

BEST PRACTICES OF MOTHER TONGUE BASED-MULTILINGUAL EDUCATION IN SAN ANTONIO DISTRICT

Melvin Paul Aunzo-Sinay

Dappat Integrated School, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13329159>

ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to identify the best practices of teachers and administrators in the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in San Antonio District, City of Ilagan, Isabela. The study used descriptive method of research this method is appropriate to the study since it tried to describe the best practices of the respondents on the implementation of the MTB-MLE in San Antonio District, San Antonio, City of Ilagan, Isabela. The respondents of the study are (7) seven School Heads and 74 teachers of Kindergarten, Grades I, II, and III. The results perceived by the respondents as best practices in MTB-MLE implementation are (a). The language and education practices of MTB-MLE have clear directions on the program; (b). MTB-MLE curriculum is aligned with the level and experience of the learners; (c). The learner's mother tongue is used as medium of instruction in school; (d). The respondents usually use real object to demonstrate concepts; and (e). School authorities impress on the learner's importance of learning the mother tongue.

Keywords: *Best Practices, Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education, Implementation*

INTRODUCTION

A child's sense of identity is said to be rooted from his or her mother tongue, but sometimes children in the Philippine schools are punished for not speaking English, which led a child to eventually view English as language of success and consequently makes

their mother tongue irrelevant. This is both psychologically and culturally damaging. Students think that they do not need to pass their mother tongue to the next generation, which would mean a significant cultural loss. However, there is nothing permanent as change. Last 2012, the format of Philippine school dramatically changed. Two major components of the K to 12 Bill that were pushed in the congress are the two-year extension in the secondary school and the implementation of Mother Tongue Based, Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). The legislation was implemented immediately of which many concerns emerged. Educators, unprepared of the dramatic change, felt so uncomfortable and some were rattled. Furthermore, parents were shocked with the fact that there is now 13 years of schooling (including kindergarten). In many cases, parents were not oriented or there was no immediate awareness-raising and mobilization. This made parents unaware of educational change such as the MTB-MLE. In addition to these, some schools, especially those in the far-flung areas lack learning modules, tools and other facilities.

The researcher being an elementary teacher in a public school has observed both positive and negative effects of the implementation of MTB-MLE on learners, teachers, and the teaching-learning process. Positively, it has been evident in the school where the researcher teaches that pupils from Kinder I to Grade III have the advantage of expressing their thoughts, opinions, and understanding in MTB-MLE with so much ease and confidence since it is their first language and at the same time the medium of instruction. It is also said that these children are learning one of the most important part of their cultural identity while studying that is the value of their mother tongue. On the other hand, as one of the teachers who teaches MTB-MLE, the researcher together with teachers in their school, personally experiences and observes that teaching in the Kinder I to Grade III is challenging because learning modules, materials, tools, and facilities are insufficient which make the teaching and learning process difficult. Also, after Grade III, pupils have a hard time in the transition period because as they reach Grade IV mother tongue is no longer the medium of instruction, but it will be the English language which is a new and completely a foreign language to them. This transition makes pupils hesitant to participate in the discussion because in their last years in school, they use their mother tongue.

There are indeed many concerns and questions from the teachers and parents with regard the implementation of the MTB-MLE in the country. Because of the many concerns and questions the goodness in the MTB-MLE implemented is not seen and appreciated by the stakeholders. In this connection therefore, this study on the best practices of Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education is undertaken, with the ultimate purpose of highlighting the MTB-MLE programs and activities that are good. When a best practice in the implementation of MTB-MLE is seen, stakeholders would better appreciate the program and would surely support its implementation, making it more successful.

Research Questions

The study aimed to find out the best practices of teachers and administrators in the implementation of the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in San Antonio District, City of Ilagan, Isabela. Specifically, it tried to the answer to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Educational attainment
 - b. Position
 - c. Length of service
 - d. Dialect used at Home
2. What are best practices in the MTB–MLE implementation as perceived by teachers and administrator?
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers on the best practices of the MTB – MLE when grouped according to their profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers and administrator on the best practice of MTB-MLE?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study made use of the descriptive method of research. According Sevilla (2006) the descriptive method is the collection, presentation, and description of data in order to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. Thus, this method is appropriate to the study since it tried to describe the best practices of the respondents on the implementation of the MTB-MLE in San Antonio District, San Antonio, City of Ilagan, Isabela.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at San Antonio District, City of Ilagan, Isabela. This district is one of the many districts in the City Division of Ilagan. Thus, the study involves the 18 elementary schools in the district of San Antonio.

Selection and Description of the Respondents

The respondents of the study are seven School Heads and the 74 teachers of Kindergarten, Grades I, II, and III in San Antonio District, SY 2016-2017.

Data Gathering Instrument

Primarily, this study made of a questionnaire adopted by the researcher from the study of Williams, Metila, Pradilla and Dido (2014). Likewise, it also made use of informal interviews and observations so as to get the general descriptions of the real observations/perceptions of teachers and administrators.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission, in writing, from to the Schools Division Superintendent (thru channel) for the conduct of the study. Upon approval, the study was conducted in various elementary schools under San Antonio District. The researcher floated the questionnaires personally and conducted informal interviews to the teachers and administrators whom he met in the schools he went to.

Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis Procedure

To address the research questions outlined in Chapter I, various treatments were used. To answer the first question on the profile of the respondents, the frequency count was used. As to the best practices of the respondent's frequency count was also used. For problems 3 and 4 chi-square was used. This looked into the difference in the perceptions of the respondents as to the best practices they have in MTB-MLE implementation.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. **What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:**
 - a. **Educational attainment**

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents
in Terms of Their Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Administrators		Teachers	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Doctoral Graduate	0	0	0	0
With Doctoral Units	0	0	0	0
Masteral Graduate	1	14	8	11
With Masteral Units	6	86	56	76
College Graduate	0	0	10	13
Total	7	100	74	100

The table 1 gives the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their educational attainment. It shows in the table that 86 percent of administrators and 76 percent of teachers are master's unit holder while only 14 percent of administrators and 11 percent of teachers are master's graduate. None has doctoral units or doctoral degree. The data above implies that many of the respondents have gone further in their studies. There looking deeper units the table, it can be decided that all the administrators meant for further studies as compared to the teachers for are only 13 percent of teachers who did not yet enroll into further studies or masteral course. Thus, they only hold the bachelor's degree.

b. Position

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents
in Terms of Position

Position	Administrators		Teachers	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Principal II	1	14	0	0
Principal I	1	14	0	0
Head Teacher III	2	29	0	0
Head Teacher I	3	43	0	0
Master Teacher II	0	0	1	1
Master Teacher I	0	0	1	1
Teacher III	0	0	30	42
Teacher II	0	0	3	4
Teacher I	0	0	37	50
Substitute Teacher	0	0	1	1
LSB Teacher	0	0	1	1
Total	7	100	74	100

The table 2 provides the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents when grouped according to position.

It shows that out of 81 respondents, 50 percent hold Teacher I position, followed by 42 percent having Teacher III position. Moreover, there are three Head Teacher I and two Head Teacher II. Also, there is one Substitute Teacher and one LSB Teacher. The table further gives a picture that in San Antonio District, most teachers hold Teacher I and Teacher III items awhile head teachers are mostly Head Teacher I item since many of them are not yet finished with their master's degree they cannot yet move to master teacher position.

c. Length of Service

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents
in Terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Administrators		Teachers	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
31-40 Years	3	43	0	0
21-30 Years	3	43	0	0
11-20 Years	1	14	21	28
6-10 Years	0	0	19	26
0-5 Years	0	0	34	46
Total	7	100	74	100

Table 3 elucidates the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to the time they serve in the Department of Education.

It shows that the 34 or 46 percent are in service for 0-5 years and 19 or 26 percent are serving the DepEd for 6-10 years. For the administrators, one or 14 percent is 11-20 years in service and three or 43 percent are 21-30 years in service.

This implies that the most of the teacher respondents are novice's teacher since they are five years and below in DepEd while administrators are quite long already in the service.

d. Dialect at Home

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents
in Terms of Their Dialect at Home

Dialect Used at Home	Administrators		Teachers	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Tagalog	0	0	4	5
Ilocano	6	86	65	88
Ibanag	1	14	5	7
Total	7	100	74	100

Table 4 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents when grouped according to the dialect used at home.

The table shows that 86 percent of the administrator’s respondent and 88 percent of the teacher respondents are Ilocano speaking. This tells that majority of the teachers and administrators are adept with the Ilocano dialect and are able to use well the Ilocano dialect as their mother tongue in school because many all of them use it at home. This finding confirms the DepEd policy that the teachers who are to teach mother tongue need to know the mother tongue by heart. The administrators likewise can supervise the teachers in their mother tongue-based instruction because they are also familiar with the language.

2. What are best practices in the MTB–MLE implementation as perceived by teachers and administrator in terms of:

a. Programs

Table 5
Frequency and Rank Distribution of the MTB-MLE
Best Practices in Terms of Programs

On Programs	Frequency	Rank
The language and education practices of MTB-MLE have clear directions.	58	1
Trainings are given to build the professional capacities of teachers.	55	2
Monitoring, evaluation and documentation are used to assess learners’ progress.	53	3
Studies for the language of the community are acceptable to mother tongue/ native speakers.	51	4
A preliminary research provided information about the language of the community.	32	5
Awareness-raising / mobilization were done to generate support for the program.	24	6

The table 5 exhibits the frequency and rank distribution of the best practices of the respondents in line with MTB-MLE.

The table tells that 58 percent of the respondents perceive that the “language and education practice of the MTB-MLE have clear directions.” This is followed by “trainings are given to build the professional capacities of the teachers with 55 teachers. However not many of the respondents perceive a “preliminary research provided information about the language of the community and an “awareness-raising/mobilization were done to generate support for the program” as a best practice in the district.

b. Instruction

Table 6
Frequency and Rank Distribution of MTB-MLE
Best Practices in Terms of Instruction

On Instruction	Frequency	Rank
MTB-MLE curriculum is aligned with the level and experience of the learners.	61	1
The local community teaches the children the dialect and culture of the place.	53	2.5
Teachers are oriented on the framework and objectives of MTB-MLE.	53	2.5
Lesson plan are provided to guide teachers.	49	4
The learner’s first exposure to reading is in mother tongue.	42	5
Teachers use list of learning outcome and indicators of learners’ experience.	38	6

Table 6 present the frequency and rank distribution of the MTB-MLE best practices in San Antonio District, City of Ilagan, Isabela in terms of instruction.

The table bares that 61 of the teachers and administrators of San Antonio District perceive that the MTB-MLE curriculum is aligned with the level and experience of the learners. On the contrary, only 38 or less than 50 percent of the respondents see the usage of list of learning outcomes and indicators of learners’ experience as practiced in their schools. Likewise, only 42 said that “the learners’ first language exposure to reading is in their mother tongue.” There are therefore perceived as not much observed in the district. This finding is similar with Walter and Trammell’s (2010) study on the effectiveness of MTB-MLE which revealed that through there was an improvement in the academic performance of the learners taught in mother tongue, still the full effect of this program on the school success of the students is emphasized as yet to be seen. Though Dekker’s Kom Experimental Mother Tongue Education Project of Cameroon, Dumatog, and

Dugiang on the Lubuangan Project in Kailanga, Philippines showed that using mother tongue contributes to the performance pupils, however, the significant gains of this MTB-MLE program will still be proved since it is still very new to the education department.

c. Language Use

Table 7
Frequency and Rank Distribution of the Respondents' MTB-MLE
Best Practices in Terms of Language Use

On Language	Frequency	Rank
Learners' mother tongue is used as medium of instruction in school.	66	1
The learners understand and can use confidently their mother tongue.	59	2
English is slowly introduced and reinforced while continuing the use of mother tongue.	51	3
Learners are proud of their mother tongue and culture and respect the mother tongue and cultures of others.	50	4
At the end of the MTB-MLE program learners have mastered and loved their mother tongue and are ready for second language learning.	46	5
The learners' proficiency in math and science improved when mother tongue is used as medium of instruction.	41	6

Table 7 reveals the frequency and rank distribution of the respondents' MTB-MLE best practices as to the language use.

The table illustrates that 66 teachers out of 74 practice the “learners' mother tongue is used as medium of instruction in school” and it ranked 1. This is followed by “the learners understand and can use confidently their mother tongue.” However, among the practices given, the item on “the learners' proficiency in science and math improved when mother tongue is used as medium of instruction” ranked last. This means that many of the respondents did not see the effect of the usage of mother tongue in the science and math proficiency of their students. It is true the pupils are able to express themselves using their mother tongue but, its effect to their math and science is not very much felt. This is maybe because most of the terms use is science and math do not have equivalent or

translation in the dialect (e.g. square root, perimeter). This finding is contradicted to the study of Toquero (2010) that using the mother tongue (Ilokano) to teach the basic concepts of numbers and operations helps build a strong foundation for the understanding and learning of higher mathematics. This approach is effective not only in getting the interest of students in the lesson but as a springboard in teaching new mathematical concepts and principles and in deepening student understanding on why mathematical operations or processes work.

d. Teaching Materials

Table 8
Frequency and Rank Distribution of the Respondents' MTB-MLE
Best Practices in Terms of Teaching Materials

On Teaching Materials	Frequency	Rank
Real objects are used to demonstrate concepts.	65	1
Picture cards are used to facilitate classroom discussion.	63	2
MTB-Materials are appropriate to the language, culture and context of the learners.	49	3
Materials are aligned with the capacities of the learners.	45	4
There are reading materials in the mother tongue.	44	5
Teaching materials/resources in the mother tongue are available/provided.	41	6

Table 8 points out the frequency and rank distribution of the respondents' MTB-MLE best practices in terms of teaching materials.

The table shows that item number 5 “real objects are used to demonstrate concepts” which ranked 1 with 65 teachers practicing it and “pictures are used to facilitate classroom discussion” ranked 2. Moreover, only 41 of the 74 teachers said that teaching materials or resources in mother tongue are provided or available. Thus, not all of the teachers therefore were given teaching materials in the teaching of mother tongue. This finding can be the reason why Wa-Mbaleka’s (2014) study on the perceptions of teachers on the mother tongue-based education result shows that teachers’ perception “could not reveal with certainty whether or not they believe an impact of MTBMLE exists on learning in general” because as stated here, not all teachers are given and provided materials in

teaching of the mother tongue-based education which is necessary in its effective implementation. The findings in the study *Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education: The Case of Cervantes District* (Sanchez, Tomas, and Pe 2023) show that some of the teachers are improvising and contextualizing instructional materials to make their instruction more meaningful and more engaging, thereby improving the performance of the learners. The teacher’s perception of contextualization goes with some works of literature. For instance, Reyes et al. (2019) testified contextualization is one of the keys to engaging the students in the teaching-learning process because they can relate their situations to their lesson. In fact, several studies claimed that contextualization significantly increases the learning of students (e.g., Chen et al., 2019; Perin, 2011; Moghaddas, 2013; Ning et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2021).

e. Stakeholders Support

Table 9
Frequency and Rank Distribution of the Respondent’ MTB-MLE
Best Practices in Terms of Stakeholders Support

On Stakeholders Support	Frequency	Rank
School authorities impress on the learners the importance of learning the mother tongue.	62	1
Parents encourage their children to learn their mother tongue.	57	2
Local and national authorities/ officials support the mother tongue program.	43	3
Local communities assist the learners in learning the mother tongue.	40	4
Local and national agencies (DOLE, DSWD...) cooperate for the implementation of the MTB-MLE.	31	5

Table 9 gives the frequency and rank distribution of the respondents’ MTB-MLE practices in terms of stakeholders’ support.

The table shows that item on 3 “School authorities impress on the learners the importance of learning the mother tongue” ranked 1 and “Parents encourage their children to learn their mother tongue” ranked 2. However, “the local and national agencies cooperate in the implementation of MTB-MLE” ranked last. This implies that this practice is not much perceived by the teachers and administrators. This finding can be attributed to the fact that though the program is pushed to be implemented and although the information dissemination is not widespread. This finding is associated with Wa-Mbaleka (2014) study that enough trainings does not seem to have occurred to allow successful implementation

as perceived by teachers of mother tongue-based education in the Philippines. Thus, parents and other stakeholders need to be included in the information drive or campaign thereby promoting the mother-tongue based multi-lingual education. Through this, schools, parents and other stakeholders can have a wider and clearer vision about the aims, goals, and objectives of MTB-MLE and that their understanding can lead them to have a complete support towards its success. As the old African proverb goes, "It takes a whole village to raise a child" give backbone to the support that this program needs. Informative drives are not necessary for parents and the community, but also to teachers alike.

3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers on the best practices of the MTB – MLE when grouped according to their profile?

a. Educational Attainment

Table 10
Results of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of Teachers
as to the Best Practices in MTB-MLE When Grouped
According to Their Educational Attainment

Educational attainment of teachers and their perceptions as to the best practices in MTB-MLE	Computed Value of	Tabular Value of	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Program	21.71	21.03	>	Reject	Significant
Instruction	28.33	18.31	>	Reject	Significant
Language	28.00	18.31	>	Reject	Significant
Material	27.51	21.01	>	Reject	Significant
Support	16.00	15.51	>	Reject	Significant

Table 10 exhibits the results of significant difference in the perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their educational attainment.

It is evident from the results that the computed Chi-square values are greater than the respective Chi-square tabular values. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perceptions of the teachers as to be the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their educational attainment. It implies that the teachers regardless of their educational qualifications perceive differently their best practices in MTB-MLE in terms of the program, instruction, language, materials and support. It can be further stated based from the findings that those teachers with master's units have more varied best practices in MTB-MLE than the other groups of teachers.

b. Position

Table 11
Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of Teachers
as to the Best Practices in MTB-MLE When
Grouped According to Their Position

Perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to position	Computed Value of	Tabular Value of	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Program	50.51	43.77	>	Reject	Significant
Instruction	47.93	37.65	>	Reject	Significant
Language	43.43	37.65	>	Reject	Significant
Material	48.92	43.77	>	Reject	Significant
Support	32.14	31.41	>	Reject	Significant

The test of significant difference in the perception of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their position is presented in table 11.

It is reflected from the test that the computed values of Chi-square are greater than their corresponding Chi-square tabular values. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, significant difference exists in the perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their position. It means that the teachers differ from each other in their perceptions as to the best practices in MTB-MLE in terms of program, instruction, language, materials, and support. In particular, Teacher I have more varied best practices in MTB-MLE than the rest of the teachers.

c. Length of Service

Table 12
Test of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of Teachers
as to the Best Practices in MTB-MLE When Grouped
According to Their Length of Service

Perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to length of service	Computed Value of	Tabular Value of	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
---	-------------------	------------------	----------	----------	---------

Program	45.43	36.42	>	Reject	Significant
Instruction	32.00	31.41	>	Reject	Significant
Language	35.80	31.41	>	Reject	Significant
Material	48.29	36.42	>	Reject	Significant
Support	26.32	26.30	>	Reject	Significant

The table 12 shows the test of significant difference in the perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their length of services.

The test reveals that the Chi-square computed values are greater than the respective Chi-square tabular values. For this reason, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their length of service. It manifests that the best practices in MTB-MLE in terms of program, instruction, language, materials, and support are perceived differently by the teachers when they are grouped according to the numbers of years of service. In particular, the teachers with 0-5 years of services have varied best practices in MTB-MLE that the rest of the teachers. This finding confirms the previous table that Teacher I (usually those new in service or 0-5 years) use more of the practices mentioned that the rest of the teachers.

d. Dialect at Home

Table 13
Test of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of Teachers
as to the Best Practices in MTB-MLE When Grouped
According to their Dialect Spoken at Home

Perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to dialect spoken	Computed Value of	Tabular Value of	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Program	23.14	21.03	>	Reject	Significant
Instruction	18.83	18.31	>	Reject	Significant
Language	24.83	18.31	>	Reject	Significant
Material	21.86	21.03	>	Reject	Significant
Support	20.00	15.51	>	Reject	Significant

The best of significant difference in the perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their dialect spoken at home is exhibited in Table 13.

It is evident from the test that the computed values of Chi-square are greater than the corresponding Chi-square tabular values. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, significant difference exists in the perceptions of teachers as to the best practices in MTB-MLE when grouped according to their dialect spoken at home. It implies that the teachers who use different dialect at home perceive the MTB-MLE best practices of San Antonio District, differently. The Ilocanos identified some with the best practices maybe because the MTB-MLE used in San Antonio District is Ilocano. It implies that the teachers with Ilocano as their dialect at home perceive differently their best practices in MTB-MLE in terms of program, instruction, language, materials, and support than those who speak Ibanag and Tagalog in the home. This finding can be attributed to the fact that Ilocano is the mother tongue taught in school.

4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers and administrator on the best practice of MTB-MLE?

Table 14
Results of Significant Difference in the Perceptions of the Teachers and Administrators as to the Best Practices in MTB-MLE

Perceptions of teachers and administrators as to the best practices in MTB-MLE	Computed Value of	Tabular Value of	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Program	22.71	12.59	>	Reject	Significant
Instruction	14.14	12.59	>	Reject	Significant
Language	12.67	11.07	>	Reject	Significant
Material	12.71	12.59	>	Reject	Significant
Support	12.80	9.49	>	Reject	Significant

Table 14 presents the results of significant difference in the perceptions of the teachers and administrators as to the best practices in MTB-MLE. It is revealed from the results that the computed values of Chi-square, are greater than the respective Chi-square tabular values. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the perceptions of the teachers and administrators as to the best practices in MTB-MLE. It implies that the teachers have different perceptions as

to the best practices in MTB-MLE along program, instruction, language, materials and support from those of the administrators. Based from the findings, the teachers apply more of the best practices in MTB-MLE than the administrators. Also, this finding can be well attributed to the result of the study of Mbaleka (2014) where it was stated that “it is not conclusive to state with certainty whether or not the Philippines is well prepared for the implementation of MTBMLE” which can explain why teachers have different perceptions as to the best practices in the program.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions are given:

Since most of the teachers are in the DepEd for 0-5 years, they are still novice teachers. Some of the teachers have not yet gone to further studies as evidenced by the 13 percent teacher respondents without master’s units. On the other hand, all administrators have gone further in their studies with 86 percent having masters unit and 14 percent master’s graduate and 43 percent of the administrator hold Head Teacher I item and many have been in the service for 21-40 years. Moreover, San Antonio is an Ilocano region, thus,

Ilocano is used as their mother tongue and majority of the teachers and administrators are proficient in the Ilocano dialect.

As to the difference in the perception of the teachers whom grouped according to their profile, it can be said that their perception significantly differs.

Likewise, the teachers and administrators MTB-MLE practices significantly differ.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusion, the researcher proposes the following:

1. Since there is a different best practice of the teachers in the implementation of the MTB-MLE, it is recommended that DepEd officials’ re-orient teachers as to the MTB-MLE program.
2. Since administrators have no formal training on MTB-MLE, DepEd needs to require them to attend one so that they would be able to guide their teachers in the implementation of the program.
3. In terms of instruction of MTB-MLE best practices the teachers and administrator use list of learning outcome and indicators of learners’ experience.
4. The DepEd should supports and provides the teachers in terms of teaching materials/resources in the mother tongue so that the implementers of MTB-MLE are fully equipped and to give best outcome of the program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research is an original study and was conducted as a basis in recommending for an appropriate and effective mode of delivery. Authors of books, journals, publications, as well as websites from the internet which were used as references in the conduct of this study are properly acknowledged and cited. Schools Division Superintendent, School Heads and Teachers consent was adopted before the conduct of this study. Further, confidentiality of the data/documents generated from the respondents' performance is highly ensured. All the data collected will solely be used for the purpose of this study.

Acknowledgments

This study is a product of great hard work and diligence of the researcher and wonderful people who contributed so much for its completion.

The researcher wishes to extend his profound gratitude to the following people who have rendered so much love and effort to accomplish this study for without them, this will not be significant and successful:

Dr. Precilo L. Buslig, Dean of the Graduate School for his help and encouragement to finish this study.

Dr. Charina G. Alejo, his adviser, for her patience, support, and word of encouragement.

Mrs. Benedicta Uy, his statistician, for the untiring guidance and effort to examine the statistical treatment and data analysis of this study.

The member of panel: Dr. Salome S. Carino, Dr. Vilma C. Cabrera, Dr. Violeta S. Directo for the significant comments and suggestions for the betterment of this study.

Mrs. Benelyn P. Jamora, Secretary of the Graduate School for the patience, support, and continuous motivation to finish this study.

Dr. Denizon P. Domingo, Schools Disision Superintendent of the Division of the City of Ilagan, for approving the letters needed in floating the questionnaire.

The Kinder to Grade 3 teachers of San Antonio District for cooperating and giving their honest and reliable response.

To his beloved parents, Melchor U. Sinay and Robelina A. Sinay, whom the researcher will always be indebted for their love and untiring support. To this siblings, Melchor A. Sinay Jr., Rey Mark A. Sinay, Ruby Mhelle A. Sinay, and his nephew, Rven Jeius A. Sinay for extending their time and love. To his sister-in-law, Venus A. Sinay, for the words of wisdom and pieces of advice. And to his relatives, who in other way have rendered their strength and time. To his love one, Mr. Bryan John V. Daluddung, who always pushing him to pursue this dream.

Lastly, to Almighty God for sustaining the researcher with needed strength and wisdom for him to accomplish this study. Without His presence this will all ho in vain.

REFERENCES

- Allen, (2002), Factors Affecting the Implementation of the MTB-MLE as Perceived by Teachers in Baguio and Benguet. Retrieved from <https://scholar.google.com.ph>
- Chen, M.P. (2019). Effects of caption and gender on junior high students' EFL learning from iMap-enhanced contextualized learning. Elsevier. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
- DepEd Order #31, Series of 2013. Retrieved from www.deped.gov.ph
- Moghaddas, B. (2013). The Effect of Contextualization on the Iranian EFL Learners' Performance in Reading Tasks. *International Journal of Educational Int. J. Adv. Multidiscipline. Res.* (2022). 9(3): 52-71 70 Science and Research (IJESR). Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Ning, N. (2017). The direct and moderating effect of learning orientation on individual performance in the banking industry in China: Contextualization of high-performance work systems. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*. Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com>
- Perin, D. (2011). Facilitating Student Learning Through Contextualization (Assessment of Evidence Series). Retrieved from <https://ccrc.tc.columbia.edu>
- R.A No. 10533, Enclosure to DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2013. Retrieved from www.deped.gov.ph
- Reyes, J.D., Insorio, A.O., Ingreso, M.V., Hilario, F.F., & Gutierrez, C.R. (2019). Conception and Application of Contextualization in Mathematics Education. *International Journal of Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 2019, 6(1), 1-18. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>
- Sanchez, Tomas and Pe, (2023), Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education: The Case of Cervantes District. Retrieved from *Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*. Retrieved from <https://al-kindipublisher.com/>
- Sevilla, Consuelo, (1997), *Methods of Research*. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com.ph/books/about/AnIntroductiontoResearchMethods>
- Toquero, E. C. (2010). Using Ilokano in teaching basic number concepts and operations in Arithmetic. *Isabela State University, Isabela*. Retrieved from <https://researchgate.net>
- Walter and Trammel, (2010), MTB-MLE in the Philippines: Perceptions, Attitudes and Outlook. Retrieved from <https://mlephilofiles.wordpress.com>
- Wang, X. (2021). Exploring the Relationship between Community College Students' Exposure to Math Contextualization and Educational Outcomes. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com>
- Wa-Mbaleka, Safary, (2014) "English Teachers' Perceptions of the Mother Tongue-Based Education Policy in the Philippines" *European Journal of Research and*

Reflection in Education in Educational Science No.4 Vol.2. Retrieved from
<https://researchgate.net>

Williams, Metila, Pardilla and Dido, (2014), Understanding Best Practices in Mother
Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in the Philippines. Retrieved from
<https://actrc.files.wordpress.com>